

**Analysis LOCAL LITERATURE AND MASS MEDIA LOCAL-
GLOBAL DIALECTICS IN USING-BANYUWANGI LITERATURE**
by Sunarti Mustamar

Cesario Zifa Harlan Alif Junior
Aquaculture – IPB University
harlanjunior33@gmail.com

Abstract

Study Indonesian literature in the mass media almost dominated review and appreciation of modern literature. writing this discusses the development of creation literature poetry and prose in relation to mass media and dialectics both of them in face globality. Multiculturalism in Indonesia is spreading at the end 1990s as a response to uniform culture since Order New capable move going to diversity. Hybridity shows that every cultural process contains a mix and interaction across limits. No there is full culture _ original and pure. Results study show that in contact with national modern culture and globally, Using literature is transformed into literature written and published through mass media (print, electronic, and digital). Hybridity literature appears in pattern modification shape, modification receptacle language with use Indonesian, as well as utilize industry creative in multimedia form and publish it through print, electronic, and digital media.

K keywords: *dialectic, global, local, mass media, literature, Using*

INTRODUCTION

The mass media in Indonesia, which have a literary rubric, tend to publish modern literary works. Classical poetry at first tends to use strict rules relating to rhyme patterns, lines, and stanzas. Using-Banyuwangi local literature which is far from the center of the kingdom develops in various forms of oral traditions. This can be seen in the stories of Jinggoan, Janger, Rengganis, folklore, mantras, and gandrung art poetry.

The poem, which is still an oral tradition, was gradually written using Latin script. In such conditions, writers are required to deal with this tendency to show their existence and local identity. This paper discusses the development of poetry and prose in relation to mass media and their dialectics in facing the challenges of modernity.

RESEARCH METHODS

The data in this paper were obtained through literature study by reading and taking an inventory of written sources in the form of literary works, poetry anthologies, transcription of poems used in ritual ceremonies, and novels. The analysis was carried out through four stages. The first is data inventory. The second is data identification. The third is data classification. Fourth, is interpretation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Local Literature and Mass Media

Efforts to store and preserve oral literature continue to be carried out by writers who care about classic stories in the form of legends and folklore. According to Saputra (2011), Using poetry at this time still continues the breath of old poetry with expressions extracted from the treasures of folk language, *basanan*, and *wangsalan*. In terms of form, the poem "*Isun Lare Using*" shows the characteristics of free modern poetry. Poets Using poets are also published in the form of song lyrics which spread to the national level.

The popularity of the song "Genjer-Genjer" was also expressed by Suprayogi, Head of the Culture and Tourism Office. With the outbreak of the G30S/PKI incident, the song "Genjer-Genjer" by Mohammad Arif, disappeared from circulation. The song was popular throughout Indonesia and became one of the identities of the Indonesian Communist Party in its heyday.

The lyric of the song "Layangan" shows the characteristics of modern poetry, which can be seen in terms of the number of lines in each stanza, the number of syllables in each line, and the rhyme pattern. In terms of content, the poem "Layangan" describes the game

of kites that are carried out in groups in the field by presenting interesting views. To stimulate the creative process of Banyuwangi artists, it is currently deemed necessary to have protection, especially for the artists.

Local-Global Dialectic

Local-global dialectic demands society to change. Changes related to knowledge, attitudes, and behavior. All of this is done by selecting, borrowing, absorbing, using, and adapting continuously. As Venn argues (in Agusta, 2007), hybridity shows an effort to take, borrow, and change oneself to respond to outsiders. Through critical hybridity studies, the concept of hybridity shows that every cultural process contains mixing and interaction across borders. The term dialectics is reminiscent of Hegel's view of thesis, antithesis, and synthesis. Local-global dialectic in Using local literature produces hybridity with several features as follows.

1. Shape Modification

The first style gives rise to literary works by using new forms that are different from those of *basanan* and *wangsalan*. The poem " *Ndeleng Seblang* " expresses the turmoil of the audience "*seblang*". The medium uses the Using language and the contents also reveal one of the Using ritual ceremonies, namely *seblang*.

2. National language

The second style brings out literary works using the Indonesian language medium, while the content only concerns the natural, social, and local cultural environment. The poem "Tarian Seblang" describes in detail the *seblang* ritual ceremony, starting from prayers and mantras to bring in spirits. The smoke of incense accompanies the strains of prayers offered to the Almighty. The hybridity of the second style has created a debate because of the view that it is called Using literature because it uses the Using language as the medium.

3. Creative Industry

Creative industry products by utilizing multimedia open up opportunities to publish literature through digital media whose distribution is global. Until now, gandrung who have entered the world of recording usually make a break-up agreement so that they only receive an honorarium once according to the agreement and not under

a royalty system. The recording industry tends to be dominated by the Kendang Kempul group. Consumer tastes are no less complicated, so it becomes a challenge for Banyuwangi artists.

4. Writing Spoken and Spoken Writing

The BEC moment is said to be a step to bridge the traditional and the modern. In his speech, the Regent of Banyuwangi stated that the carnival was initiated to bridge traditional and modern arts so that they can be accepted by the international community. The emergence of a creative industry in the form of a multimedia production house is an effort to verbalize the written. It has a strategic role in communities that are still strong in the oral tradition and weak in the written tradition.

CONCLUSION

Based on this paper, it can be concluded that Using literature is rooted in oral tradition. When there is cultural contact with modern, national and global culture, Using literature shows dynamics. Literary hybridity appears in the form of modification of the form and modification of language containers using Indonesian.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Altman, R. (2021). 3. A Semantic/Syntactic Approach to genre films. In *Film genre reader IV* (pp. 27-41). University of Texas Press.
- Barus , IRG, Simanjuntak , MB, & Resmayasari , I. (2021). READING LITERACIES THROUGH EVIETA-BASED LEARNING MATERIAL: STUDENTS'PERCEPTIONS (Study Case Taken from Vocational School–IPB University). *JOURNAL OF ADVANCED ENGLISH STUDIES* , 4 (1), 15-20.
- Bateman, J., & Schmidt, KH (2013). *Multimodal film analysis: How films mean* . Routledge.
- Bednarek , M. (2015). Corpus-assisted multimodal discourse analysis of television and film narratives. In *Corpora and discourse studies* (pp. 63-87). Palgrave Macmillan, London.
- Bellour , R. (2000). *The analysis of films* . Indiana University Press.
- Benshoff , H. (2015). *Film and television analysis: An introduction to methods, theories, and approaches* . Routledge.
- Bernadtua , M., Rafli , Z., & Boeriswati , E. (2022, January). LANGUAGES ACQUISITION AND TEACHING IN KELAPA GADING–NORTH JAKARTA (CASE STUDY TAKEN AT SAINT PETER'S JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL). In *UICELL Conference Proceedings* (pp. 162-170).
- Bittau , F., Potamialis , C., Togay , M., Abbas, A., Isherwood, PJ, Bowers, JW, & Walls, JM (2018). Analysis and optimization of the glass/TCO/MZO stack for thin film CdTe solar cells. *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells* , 187 , 15-22.
- Carr , D. (2019). Methodology, representation, and games. *Games and Culture* , 14 (7-8), 707-723.
- Condon, WS, & Ogston , WD (1966). Sound film analysis of normal and pathological behavior patterns. *Journal of nervous and mental diseases* .
- Estrada, LM, Hielscher , E., Koolen , M., Olesen , CG, Noordegraaf , J., & Blom , J. (2017). Film analysis as annotation: Exploring current tools. *Moving Image: The Journal of the Association of Moving Image Archivists* , 17 (2), 40-70.
- Franco, A., Magnani , A., & Maio , D. (2020). A multimodal approach for human activity recognition based on skeleton and RGB data. *Pattern Recognition Letters* , 131 , 293-299.

- Geiger, J., & Rutsky, RL (Eds.). (2013). *Film analysis: A Norton reader* . WW Norton & Company.
- Henseler , C. (2021). Finding Humanity. *The Scholar as Human: Research and Teaching for Public Impact* , 129.
- Jahn , M. (2003). A guide to narrative film analysis. *Poems, Plays, and Prose: A Guide to the Theory of Literary Genres* , 2 .
- Kendrick, M. (2016). *Literacy and multimodality across global sites* . Routledge.
- Kozlarek , O. (2015). Introduction: Crossing Borders, Reaching Humanity. In *Octavio Paz* (pp. 9-16). transcript- Verlag .
- Liu, AA, Xu, N., Nie , WZ, Su, YT, Wong, Y., & Kankanhalli , M. (2016). Benchmarking a multimodal and multiview and interactive dataset for human action recognition. *IEEE Transactions on cybernetics* , 47 (7), 1781-1794.
- Lo, HF, Wu, IW, & Ni, CC (2018, July). Representation of Memory in Design for Humanity. In *International Conference on Cross-Cultural Design* (pp. 43-57). Springer, Cham.
- Magnusson, P., & Godhe , AL (2019). Multimodality in Language Education-- Implications for Teaching. *Designs for Learning* , 11 (1), 127-137.
- Parc , J. (2018). Evaluating the effects of protectionism on the film industry: A case study analysis of Korea. In *Handbook of State Aid for Film* (pp. 349-366). Springer, Cham.
- Pattiwael , AS (2019). Literature for Developing Student's Humanity Awareness. In *Journal International Seminar on Languages, Literature, Arts, and Education (ISLLAE)* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 79-88).
- Peña-Cervel , MS (2016). Motivating film title translation: a cognitive analysis. *CRCULO de Linguística Aplicada a la Comunicación* , 66 , 31.
- Plate, L. (2015). How to do things with literature in the digital age: Anne Carson's Nox , multimodality, and the ethics of bookishness. *Contemporary Women's Writing* , 9 (1), 93-111.
- Richards, M. (2016). Film Music Themes: Analysis and Corpus Study. *Music Theory Online* , 22 (1).
- Rosenberg, FJ (2016). *After Human Rights: Literature, Visual Arts, and Film in Latin America, 1990-2010* . University of Pittsburgh Press.
- Rouast , PV, Adam, MT, & Chiong , R. (2019). Deep learning for human affect recognition: Insights and new developments. *IEEE Transactions on Affective Computing* , 12 (2), 524-543.

- Santos, RB, & de Oliveira, UR (2019). Analysis of occupational risk management tools for the film and television industry. *International Journal of Industrial Ergonomics* , 72 , 199-211.
- Serafini , F. (2015). Multimodal literacy: From theories to practices. *Language Arts* , 92 (6), 412-423.
- Simanjuntak , MB (2021). METAMORPHIC ANALYSIS IN SONG LYRICS BATAK TOBA “AUT BOI NIAN” WRITTEN BY WERVIN PANGGABEAN. *JOURNAL OF ADVANCED ENGLISH STUDIES* , 4 (1), 34-39.
- Simanjuntak , MB., Suseno , M., Ramdhoni , R., Mayuni , I., Zuriyati , Z., & Sutrisno , S. (2022). The Value of Parents' Image in Seven Batak Toba Songs (Literary Art Study). *Tambusai Journal of Education* , 6 (2), 8540–8551.
- Simanjuntak , MB, & Barus , IRG (2020). English Reading Literacies to Improve Values Among Teenagers. *SELTICS* , 93-102.
- Simanjuntak , MB, & Lumingkewas , MS (2022). THE WOMAN IN THE BOOK OF KINGS (LITERARY STUDIES AND HERMENEUTICS). In *UICELL Conference Proceeding* (pp. 328-334).
- Simanjuntak , MB, Barus , IRG, & Resmayasari , I. (2021). ANALYSIS OF VIOLENCE IN CITY OF GOD FILM DIRECTED BY FERNANDO MEIRELLES. *JOURNAL OF ADVANCED ENGLISH STUDIES* , 4 (1), 1-6.
- Simanjuntak , MB, Barus , IRG, & Resmayasari , I. (2021). Analysis of Song" My Hands Na Metmet " by Using Translation Techniques into English. In *UICELL Conference Proceeding* (pp. 195-202).
- Simanjuntak , MB, Lumingkewas , MS, & Sutrisno , S. (2021). ANALYSIS OF TANGIANG ALE AMANAMI (OUR FATHER) USING THE TECHNIQUES OF TRANSLATION. *JOURNAL OF ADVANCED ENGLISH STUDIES* , 4 (2), 70-75.
- Simanjuntak , MB, Rahmat , A. . , Setiadi , S. . , Suseno , M. . , Romdani , R., & Lumingkewas , MS . (2022). Power Relations in the Story of “ Nommensen Meets King Panggalamei ” by Patar Pasaribu . *Tambusai Journal of Education* , 6 (2), 8552–8557.
- Simanjuntak , MB, Suseno , M., & Setiadi , S. (2022). THE EFFECTIVENESS OF MICROSOFT OFFICE 365 AS AN ONLINE ENGLISH LEARNING MEDIA. In *UICELL Conference Proceedings* (pp. 25-32).
- Simanjuntak , MB, Suseno , M., Setiadi , S., Lustyantie , N., & Barus , IRGRG (2022). Integration of Curricula (Curriculum 2013 and Cambridge Curriculum for Junior High School Level in Three Subjects) in Pandemic Situation. *Ideas: Journal of Education, Social, and Culture* , 8 (1), 77-86.

- Simanjuntak , MB, Sutrisno , S., & Lumingkewas , MS (2021). LITERARY STUDY “NOMMENSEN, APOSTLE IN BATAKNESE”. *JOURNAL OF ADVANCED ENGLISH STUDIES* , 4 (2), 42-45.
- Simanjuntak , MB, Zuriyati , Z., & Lustyantie , N. (2022). METAMORPHIC ANALYSIS IN SONG LYRICS BATAK TOBA “JUJUNG GOARHI AMANG ”(STUDY OF PORTRAY OF PARENTS). *PROJECT (Professional Journal of English Education)* , 5 (1), 236-243.
- Simanjuntak , MB, Zuriyati , Z., Utami , SR, & Lumingkewas , MS (2022). Nommensen and Bataknese (The Representation of Apostle). *Budapest International Research and Critics Institute (BIRCI-Journal): Humanities and Social Sciences* , 5 (2), 9291-9297.
- Sleman , SM, & Fahmi , IM (2020). The Destiny of Humanity in the Future Cities of Ray Bradbury. *Zanco Journal of Humanity Sciences* , 24 (1), 278-288.
- Teixeira, MBM, da Costa Galvao , LL, Mota -Santos, CM, & Carmo , LJO (2020). Women and work: film analysis of Most Beautiful Thing. *Revista de Gestão* .
- Way, LC, & McKerrell , S. (2017). *Music as multimodal discourse: Semiotics, power and protest* . Bloomsbury Publishing.
- Wellek , R. (2018). *The attack on literature and other essays* . UNC Press Books.
- Widjayanti , EP (2019). Building Humanity Values Through Maya Angelou's poems. In *Journal International Seminar on Languages, Literature, Arts, and Education (ISLLAE)* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 143-148).
- Wildfeuer , J. (2014). *Film discourse interpretation: Towards a new paradigm for multimodal film analysis* . Routledge.
- Wu, J., & Yan, Y. (2016, November). Study of humanity teaching model in higher vocational school Chinese teaching. In *Proceedings of the 4th International Conference on Management Science, Education Technology, Arts, Social Science and Economics* (Vol. 85, pp. 1855-1858).